

Mobile Usage Among College Students: An Investigation

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Abstract

Mobile technology demonstrates significant potential for boosting information exchange activities, on and off campus, between students and faculty in higher education institutions. Students' access to, usage of, and attitudes toward mobile devices, their functions, capabilities, and social media apps were investigated in this study. Smartphone usage among college students is prevalent in daily life, according to a poll of 308 students at Kuwait's College of Business Studies (CBS) who were asked about their mobile technology usage. The findings revealed that students had a positive opinion of mobile capabilities and functionalities, and that social media apps, like Instagram, Snap Chat, and Twitter, were in widespread use. Significant disparities were observed between genders in terms of mobile usage. In terms of using mobile native features and applications, male students were found to be substantially more active than female students.

Keywords

Mobile technology; higher education (HE); Mobile usage; Mobile native functions; Social media

1. Introduction

Mobile phones have been in use since the 1970s, with Motorola producing the first handheld mobile phone in 1973. After several decades of being used purely as a communication device, mobile phones are now utilized for both voice and text communication. Smartphones, or mobile phones with a mobile operating system, have received a major upgrade in their ability to imitate a portable personal computer with a mobile operating system [1]. With the advent of the Apple iPhone and Google Android OS in 2007 and 2008, respectively, the next generation of cellphone became a worldwide craze. Tablets are a relatively recent addition to the mobile device lineup following the introduction of the iPad and several Android variations in the 2010s. Personal computing devices are increasingly becoming mobile. Mobile devices are the most popular and fascinating technical tools that have fundamentally transformed the face of communication and influenced people's psychosocial behaviors. A huge proportion of students own smartphones and efficiently use them for communication and information gathering [2].

A smartphone is a phone with several functionalities in addition to allowing the user to make phone calls. At the same time, mobile phones offer various characteristics that enable the user to perform tasks that were previously not possible on a mobile phone [3]. Mobile devices and applications with ever-expanding capacities are becoming increasingly common. Berking et al. (2013) argue that mobile devices' unique features, such as connection, mobility, GPS, and cameras, offer a lot of promise to improve students' learning experience [4]. The widespread availability of mobile devices has a significant impact on academics' and students' knowledge-sharing activities. This

improved access offers students a certain level of convenience by providing additional methods for them to engage with their educational campuses, course materials, and peers. The distinction between native mobile apps and specialized mobile web apps was clarified by [5]. Native applications are those that have been built and developed particularly for a mobile operating system. Google's Android, Apple's iOS, and Microsoft's Windows Phone are the three most popular mobile operating systems at present. Android is based on the Java programming language, while iOS is based on the Objective C programming language. Dedicated mobile web apps, on the other hand, are web applications that are planned and built to closely resemble the native programs of the host operating system; however, they run in a web browser on the host platform.

Higher education institutions acknowledge that the purpose of a mobile initiative should focus on integrated student services both on and off campus as the number of educational bodies grows and technology improves. The annual EDUCAUSE review poll found a significant growth in the ownership and use of mobile devices for educational purposes between 2013 and 2014 [6]. Similarly, Kuwait's mobile penetration is expected to reach over 200 percent by 2020 [7]. The researchers were prompted to perform the current study because of the widespread availability of mobile phones among Kuwaitis.

Although there have been numerous theoretical studies on mobile services and mobile apps, a substantial number of studies used particular questioning strategies to assess consumers' preferences. The great majority of these polls found that mobile devices are becoming more important in everyday life and that advancements and features are becoming more popular [8, 3, 4]. However, the success of those functions, services, and applications depends heavily on the security of the underlying mobile technologies [9, 10].

This study investigates the use and perceptions of mobile native functions, capabilities, and apps to assist on-campus and off-campus students (CBS) at the College of Business Studies. The college is part of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training (PAAET) in Kuwait, which has over ten thousand students and more than fifty thousand at PAAET, making it Kuwait's largest Higher Education (HE) school. A study of 308 CBS students was undertaken to learn more about how they use and perceive mobile technology. The results of this research can aid the developers of the recently released CBS mobile application in maximizing mobile capabilities and improving the app's usefulness for future enhancements.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 deals with the literature review. The approach for this investigation is explained in Section 3. Section 4 summarizes the findings, while Section 5 concludes the research findings and recommends future research directions.

2. Literature Review

The rising power and capabilities of smartphones, in combination with increased demand, entails that the market for mobile apps has grown exponentially in recent years. The creation of feature-rich apps has been aided by advancements in the global positioning system, battery life, camera, displays, and CPU. Online banking, shopping, social networking, instant messaging, voice chat, email, file sharing, and gaming are all common mobile application functionalities [11]. Many of the apps have been implemented in the corporate world to aid in the performance of business operations. These mobile apps provide a better user experience as an outcome of enhanced screen resolution, touch screens, longer battery life, and the ability to operate on many devices [12, 13]. Many theoretical studies have been conducted on mobile services, functionalities, and apps, with a considerable amount of research focusing on user preferences and usage. The great majority of the extant studies suggested that mobile devices are becoming more important in everyday life and that new capabilities and functionalities are being used more often [8, 2, 3, 14, 15]. The goal of a study performed by [16] was to find predictors of problematic smartphone usage among university students based on demographic variables, loneliness, social app use, and smartphone model. 257 Brazilian university students participated in this cross-sectional study, answering a smartphone addiction scale, a questionnaire regarding smartphone usage trends, and the Brazilian version of the UCLA-R scale. Women, iPhone owners, and Instagram and Snapchat users all exhibited much greater levels of smartphone addiction. They discovered a link between the significance assigned to WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, and Snapchat on the Brazilian version of the smartphone addiction scale.

Ataş & Elik [17] emphasized the objectives, patterns, and conditions of smartphone use among university students in developing countries. A total of 842 university students from 101 different universities took part in the study, which involved a cross-sectional survey. In terms of usage habits, they found that most university students had been using their cellphones for roughly three years, primarily at night and for about five hours each day. They also used their mobile phones to access the Internet for roughly 4 hours every day. According to the findings, the most common reasons for using a smartphone were texting and communicating with others, followed by checking social media and performing online research. University students mostly use smartphones to pass the time when they are bored, alone, or waiting for someone. Alsayed, Bano, and Alnajjar [2] performed a similar study to assess the usage of smartphones among undergraduate nursing students for instructional reasons. A survey was performed at King Saud University for Health Sciences' College of Nursing. According to the findings, 94.8 percent of students had their phones with them at all times. A substantial percentage of students (77.8%) said they used their cellphones to take notes in class, while 24.4 percent said they always used them in clinical situations. The most common usage of cellphones was to obtain information from websites (93.3 percent), which was reported more frequently in group studies than in individual studies. A substantial number of pupils claimed to be members of a WhatsApp study group (89.6 percent). 85.2 percent of respondents said they used social media sites for academic purposes.

Soegoto [3] conducted a quantitative study to acquire a more in-depth understanding of smartphone usage among Indonesian college students. The results revealed that students may select a given smartphone because of its complete features, affordability, popularity, operating system, quality, games, and camera features, according to the findings. Students used their smartphones for approximately 6 hours every day, with only 2-4 hours being dedicated to social events. The outcomes also revealed that pupils read for less than 2 hours on average. Instagram, Line, and WhatsApp were some of the most widely used smartphone applications. The practice of placing a smartphone by the bed was also common. Furthermore, [18] discovered that mobile

technologies enabled users in HE institutions to perform nine tasks, including sending photos/videos to colleagues, using the mobile as an audio player, accessing information or services on the web, making video calls, taking photos, or recording movies, sending or receiving email, using the mobile as a personal organizer, sending or receiving SMS, and calling colleagues or others. In addition, at a Brazilian higher education institution, [14] investigated student and teacher opinions of personal mobile device usage for suitable practices. Significant disparities in views were also studied and documented, as well as correlations between perceptions and demographic data.

Mobile devices enable teachers and students to teach and study in places other than traditional classrooms [19]. When comparing survey findings from 2012 to 2014, researchers discovered that the percentage of people who used their smartphones for studying grew significantly from 58 percent to 77 percent [20]. A survey on student utilization of mobile devices was undertaken by Sheffield University. Students used their cellphones on campus for internet browsing (88 percent), social networking (88 percent), academic services and resources (78 percent), and emailing, according to the findings (69 percent). Smartphones were the most popular on campus when compared to laptops and tablets. According to [21], smartphones (87 percent) are utilized more in lectures than any other gadget. [22] offered students' perspectives on the extent to which mobile devices facilitated studying in higher education contexts. The findings highlighted the educational benefits of mobile devices for pupils. Students were able to access material more rapidly using mobile computing devices. Mobile devices' constant connectivity enabled students to converse with peers in a more contextual manner [19]. A similar research study [23] examined 316 university students in a developing country's present academic usage of cellphones. All of the respondents used their smartphones to search the Internet for relevant information, and the majority of them (62.3 percent) did so many times each day. Respondents also reported that they used their cellphones to access academic resources (65.5%), read news (63.3%), use social media (60.1%), access sports news (40.8%), enjoy themselves (37.9%), and listen to music (37.6 percent).

O'Connor and Andrews [24] employed a self-reported questionnaire based on a study of the literature to learn about undergraduate nursing students' views on the use of cellphones and mobile technologies to promote learning in clinical settings. A total of 200 nursing students from a four-year Bachelor of Nursing program participated in the survey, which was based on descriptive data. Calculators, pharmacological reference manuals, and medical dictionaries were all utilized with varying degrees of regularity. Mobile technology provided various benefits to nursing students, including improved access to instructional materials, increased knowledge and confidence, and reduced worry about learning in practice. Barriers were also discovered, including nursing staff's unfavorable attitudes, limited Wi-Fi access, and the quality of training information offered on mobile apps.

The adoption and usage of mobile devices as a source of Egyptian university students' news was investigated in a 2019 study [25]. A random sample of 400 university students, all of whom owned cellphones, were used in the study. The uses and satisfaction theory drove this investigation of the usage of cellphones as a news resource among university students. A survey was employed as part of the study's quantitative research technique. Between March and April 2018, data was gathered utilizing a self-administered questionnaire. Despite the fact that Egypt is not an oil-rich country, the majority of university students were strong smartphone users, with the clear majority (87.5%) obtaining news via their cellphones. More crucially, the research indicated that university students primarily utilized cellphones to obtain general information (47.5%), Egyptian news (37.5%), entertainment (29.25%), and to keep up with international events (27.75%). Finally, the research revealed that 70% of students used their cellphones to keep up with current

events, and 67.5 percent stated that smartphones helped them interact with their peers.

Faculty impressions of students' usage of personal devices in the classroom have also been studied [26]. According to the data, some professors prohibit smartphone use in the classroom, while others disregard it and embrace it to enhance the classroom experience. Similarly, [27] investigated teacher educators' views on the usage of mobile devices in the classroom. According to the findings, the teachers involved in the study believed that the advantages of adopting mobile devices in their classrooms outweigh the risks. Without a doubt, educators' IT skills will aid in the effective usage of mobile technologies. The attitude of the instructors and their lack of prior understanding of IT use are two important elements that influence the technology's acceptability [28]. O'bannon and Thomas [29] performed a further study involving 1095 teachers from two states in the southeast United States. The study looked at the association between teachers' age and the type of phone they used, their support for using phones in the classroom, and their opinions of the benefits of mobile features and capabilities. The findings revealed that the age of the teachers is important. Teachers under the age of 32 and those between the ages of 33 and 49 had no significant differences; however, there were substantial disparities between instructors above the age of 50 and younger teachers. Older teachers were less likely to possess mobile devices, were less supportive across the board, and were less enthusiastic about mobile features and capabilities.

3. STUDENTS' PERCEPTIONS OF MOBILE FUNCTIONS: A CASE STUDY

This section explains how the study was performed at Kuwait HE's College of Business Studies (CBS) and presents the results. In order to uncover crucial aspects that promote the proper adoption of mobile devices in higher education institutions, a framework was established to investigate students' views of mobile devices and their applications. The framework was based on the principles of systems thinking [30]. The description of the framework begins with the identification of a system and the definition of its boundaries and stakeholders. The system under question is Kuwait's educational institutions. The high-priority stakeholders, mainly CBS students, were the subjects of interest.

3.1 Participants

The survey included 308 students from the College of Business Studies, of which there were 109 males and 199 females (CBS). Students from various areas and levels of study were included in the sample. Table 1 shows how the research sample was distributed based on demographic factors.

3.2 Evaluation Tools

For this topic, a survey was deemed to be an acceptable research tool. Several prior research studies were used to build and customize an online questionnaire [31, 14, 8, 32, 33, 34]. The questions and scales used in the tool were deemed to be appropriate for the study's scope. The questionnaire was divided into three sections. Part 1 captured demographic data as well as information on how frequently mobile devices are used. Part 2 of the survey looked at the use of mobile native functionalities and capabilities, while Part 3 investigated how frequently people used popular social networking apps. Students were given an online questionnaire to complete in order to assess their use of mobile device native features and applications.

3.3 Data Analysis

SPSS was used to analyze the data gathered via the online questionnaire. In this study, percentages, mean, and standard deviations (SD) were computed and compared. The mean was used to determine how much individual replies to a question varied or "deviated" from the mean, whereas SD was used to determine how far individual responses to a question varied or "deviated" from the mean [35]. To give an impartial assessment

of any differences detected between means in two unrelated groups, an independent-sample t-test was utilized. The t-test was employed in this study to compute if there was a statistically significant difference between variables of the obtained data based on the gender of the pupils. The significance threshold (sig.) was set at 0.05. To begin, a t-test was used to determine how students used mobile services and applications differently. The disparities in students' frequency of usage of social media apps were then investigated. At two-week intervals, an online survey was sent out at random via email, social media, and e-messaging platforms. To test the questionnaire's appropriateness, a pilot study was conducted. The questionnaire had a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.90, indicating that it was trustworthy and could be utilized confidently with the primary research population.

4. RESULTS & FINDINGS

This section includes the study's results and conclusions, such as demographic information about the students, their usage of mobile native functionalities, and their regular use of mobile-based social networking applications.

4.1. Demographics

Table 1 shows the responses to the three questions (gender, age, and frequency of using mobile devices) (1). The majority of the participants (308 students) were female (65%), with the majority of them (95%) being between the ages of 17 and 24, and (88%) always using mobile phones and (12%) using them sometimes.

Table I. Demographics

Gender	Male	35%
	Female	65%
Age	17 - 24	95%
	25 and more	5%
How often do you use your mobile phone	Always (More than 3 hours a day)	88%
	Sometimes (Less than 1 hour a day)	12%
	Seldom (Less than 1 hour a day)	0%
	I don't use it	0%

4.2. Usage of Mobile Native Functions

Figure (1) depicts the percentage of students that utilized mobile native services and applications on a frequent basis. Photo and video albums, for example, were utilized by 96% of the respondents; WhatsApp was also used by 96% of people (91 percent). SMS, on the other hand, was used the least by students (27 percent), which might be attributed to the significant usage of WhatsApp, a free program with innovative functions [36]. It's also worth noting that the pupils made extensive use of photography, video, and cameras.

Fig. 1. Students' Use of Mobile Functions and Applications

According to the data presented in Figure 1, 80 percent of students used their mobile phones to access the Internet. Furthermore, the majority of students (68%) utilized their mobile phones to learn. This is significant because it indicates that students are prepared to adopt m-learning as a formal technique for future study, in which they utilize mobile phones in the same manner that they use laptop computers. As such, mobile phones demonstrate the potential to support learning processes. Calendar (82 percent), camera (90 percent), clock (91 percent), web browsing (80 percent), games (62 percent), email (76 percent), translation (88 percent), voice recording (56 percent), taking notes (79 percent), browsing maps (80 percent), album (96 percent), social media (82 percent), and e-learning (68 percent) were among the other uses of mobile functions and capabilities the participants described. These findings are backed up by a significant body of evidence [2, 23, 16, 21].

Table (2) demonstrates the varied usage of mobile phones by (male/female) respondents based on their replies to questions 1 to 16. Students rely extensively on mobile functionalities and can use their phones to get knowledge and information on the Internet. Table (2) also shows how well students know how to use various apps on their mobile devices. Students are acclimated to mobile

functions and apps, such as mobile devices as vital information sources, cameras and albums, messaging, calendars, clocks, maps, and social media, according to the research. These findings are in line with others [8, 32, 2, 14]. Students' frequent use of WhatsApp, albums, and cameras for content and non-content activities, as well as a tendency to utilize a few additional programs for content, administrative, management, and amusement purposes, were also discovered.

T-tests, mean, and SD were used to identify the descriptive statistics. As demonstrated in Table (2), there were significant disparities in how male and female students used mobile features. Gender disparities do occur, as this study has shown. Males make more phone calls than females, it appears. Males are also more likely than females to use "WhatsApp," "Calendar," "Camera," "Alarm/Clock," "Browsing the Web," "Games," "Sending Email," "Maps," and "Photo and Video Album." Females, on the other hand, "browse the web" and "play games" more than men. Males tend to be more active in utilizing these mobile functions than females. This research is backed up by the findings of [37], who found that Kuwaiti males are more likely than females to upload personal photos on Instagram and expose personal information.

TABLE II. STUDENTS' USE OF MOBILE FUNCTIONS AND APPLICATIONS (BY GENDER)

	Mobile Native Functions and applications	Yes	No	I don't Know	Mean	SD	Sig	
1	Call	Male	91%	6%	3%	2.83	.553	.000
		Female	77%	5%	18%	2.59	.779	
2	SMS/MMS	Male	34%	60%	6%	2.25	.596	.679
		Female	23%	46%	31%	1.95	.706	
3	WhatsApp	Male	91%	3%	6%	3.00	.000	.000
		Female	86%	5%	9%	2.77	.598	
4	Calendar	Male	86%	8%	6%	2.83	.373	.000
		Female	80%	14%	6%	2.73	.617	
5	Camera	Male	86%	14%	0%	2.92	.277	.000
		Female	83%	15%	2%	2.81	.496	
6	Alarm/ Clock	Male	91%	9%	0%	2.92	.277	.019
		Female	91%	5%	5%	2.86	.457	
7	Browsing the Web	Male	80%	17%	3%	2.83	.553	.008
		Female	83%	12%	5%	2.91	.417	
8	Games	Male	43%	43%	14%	2.26	.725	.000
		Female	72%	23%	5%	2.68	.557	
9	Sending Email	Male	91%	0%	9%	2.83	.553	.000
		Female	68%	23%	9%	2.59	.651	
10	Translate	Male	86%	14%	0%	2.83	.373	.479
		Female	89%	6%	5%	2.86	.457	
11	Voice Recording	Male	60%	34%	6%	2.50	.647	.732
		Female	54%	35%	11%	2.45	.656	
12	Taking Notes	Male	82%	9%	9%	2.75	.596	.885
		Female	77%	18%	5%	2.73	.538	
13	Maps	Male	94%	3%	3%	3.00	.000	.000
		Female	72%	23%	5%	2.68	.555	
14	Photo and Video Album	Male	100%	0%	0%	3.00	.000	.000

		Female	94%	4%	2%	2.91	.288	
15	Social Media	Male	74%	26%	0%	2.74	.439	.078
		Female	86%	9%	5%	2.82	.490	
16	e- Learning Purposes	Male	74%	17%	9%	2.66	.627	.143
		Female	65%	35%	0%	2.64	.482	

4.3. Social Media Usage Among Students

Part 3 of the survey looked at how often students used social media apps, including Twitter, Instagram, Facebook, YouTube, Snapchat, and LinkedIn, as shown in Figure (2) and Table 1. (3). Students' cooperation, engagement, and interaction can all benefit from social media tools, as can their involvement and engagement [38]. Figure 2 depicts how students utilize social media apps. Snapchat is constantly utilized by students (56.0%), followed by Twitter (53%), Instagram (44.0%), and YouTube (44.0%). (44.0 percent). Participants, on the other hand, showed little interest in LinkedIn, with 88.0 percent saying they don't use it and 71.0 percent saying they don't use Facebook. These findings can aid in determining which social media applications can be used to execute m-learning. Instructors and developers should be aware that video-based social media apps like Snapchat and YouTube

are popular among students. Furthermore, there is evidence of a favorable attitude toward adopting mobile as a social learning tool since it allows students and instructors to collaborate. By employing social media tools, students and instructors felt more optimistic about mobile learning.

Table (3) illustrates that there are considerable disparities in how male and female students use social media apps, including Instagram, YouTube, SnapChat, Twitter, and Facebook. When it came to utilizing LinkedIn, however, there was no discernible difference between men and women. Furthermore, Males prefer "Instagram" and "YouTube," whilst Females choose "Snap Chat" and "Twitter." The least utilized programs were found to be "Facebook" and "LinkedIn." This can be explained by the fact that these applications are not popular among Kuwaiti students. These findings are in line with others [39, 40, 41, 42].

TABLE II. STUDENTS' FREQUENT USE OF SOCIAL MEDIA APPLICATIONS (BY GENDER)

	Frequent use of social media	Gender	Always	Sometimes	Seldom	I don't use it	Mean	SD	Sig
1.	Instagram	Male	51%	31%	9%	9%	3.26	.927	.029
		Female	40%	40%	18%	2%	3.22	.739	
2.	YouTube	Male	60%	34%	6%	0%	3.50	.647	.007
		Female	35%	32%	28%	5%	2.99	.907	
3.	Snap Chat	Male	54%	9%	26%	9%	3.17	1.070	.000
		Female	55%	42%	3%	0%	3.50	.585	
4.	Twitter	Male	35%	17%	31%	17%	2.66	1.107	.003
		Female	63%	18%	11%	8%	3.37	.980	
5.	Facebook	Male	0%	26%	26%	49%	1.74	.832	.000
		Female	5%	1%	12%	82%	1.27	.687	
6.	LinkedIn	Male	0%	0%	17%	83%	1.17	.381	.465
		Female	4%	0%	5%	91%	1.18	.649	

Fig. 2. Students' Frequent Use of Social Media Applications

The findings of this study may be used to determine which social media applications can be used when creating a new mobile app for students and teachers. Developers should keep in mind that video-based social media apps like Snapchat, YouTube, and Instagram are popular among students.

I. CONCLUSION & FUTURE DIRECTIONS

This study employed a survey-based technique to collect data from 308 HE students at the College of Business Studies (CBS) in Kuwait. The study's primary goal was to learn more about CBS students' habits and frequency of usage of smartphone devices, as well as their preferred mobile device functionalities and the everyday tasks to which they may contribute. Students' frequent use of certain applications and functions, such as WhatsApp, photo and video albums, and cameras, for content and non-content activities, as well as a tendency to use a few other mobile functions and applications for content, administrative, management, and entertainment purposes, were discovered. The results of the survey suggested that students were willing to use their phones for both on and off campus activities. Furthermore, they felt that m-learning may help them reach their educational goals and that utilizing mobile phones in and out of the classroom could help them learn faster. Gender and cellphone usage were shown to have significant disparities. In terms of using mobile native features and applications, male students were found to be substantially more active than female students. To design acceptable and useful mobile applications, the research advises continual dialogue between professors and students, as well as among students themselves. Because the college is preparing to establish a mobile application for CBS students, instructors, staff, and families, the goal of this study is to properly employ these mobile native functionalities.

In terms of future study, gender segregation exists in Kuwait's higher education system due to cultural and religious standards. Male and female students are anticipated to face uneven chances and obstacles in terms of access to educational institutions and social engagement. More studies are needed to find solutions to this problem, such as offering equal chances for male and female students and bridging the gender gap. In addition, future study for this project could focus on Kuwaiti ladies' online social environment. Kuwaiti female students may be able to overcome social and cultural barriers and assert their rights as a result of research of this nature.

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